

Title

Update on analytical methods and research gaps in the use of household consumption and expenditure survey data to inform the design of food fortification programs

Running title

Secondary data to design fortification programs

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Abbreviations

AME, adult male equivalent

DALY, disability-adjusted life year

EAR, estimated average requirement

FCT, food composition table
FACT, Fortification Coverage Assessment Toolkit
FAFH, foods consumed away from home
GAIN, Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition
HCES, household consumption and expenditure survey
IFA, iron-folic acid
LSMS, Living Standards Measurement Study
LMIC, low- and middle-income country
SES, socioeconomic status
UL, tolerable upper intake level
WRA, women of reproductive age

1 Update on analytical methods and research gaps in the use of household consumption and expenditure
2 survey data to inform the design of food fortification programs

3 **Abstract**

4 The lack of nationally representative, individual-level dietary intake data has led researchers to
5 increasingly turn to household-level data on food acquisitions and/or consumption to inform the design
6 of food fortification programs in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). These nationally-
7 representative, household-level data come from Household Consumption and Expenditure Surveys
8 (HCESs), which are collected regularly in many LMICs and are often made publicly available. Our
9 objectives were to examine the utility of HCES data to inform the design of food fortification programs
10 and to identify best-practice methods for analyzing HCES data for this purpose. To this end, we
11 summarized information needed to design fortification programs and assessed the extent to which HCES
12 data can provide corresponding indicators. We concluded that HCES data are well-suited to guide the
13 selection of appropriate food vehicles, but because individual-level estimates of apparent nutrient
14 intakes rely on assumptions about the intrahousehold distribution of food, more caution is advised
15 when using HCES data to select the target micronutrient content of fortified foods. We also developed a
16 checklist to guide analysts through the use of HCES data, and, where possible, identified research-based,
17 best-practice analytical methods for analyzing HCES data, including selecting the number of days of
18 recall data to include in the analysis and converting reported units to standard units. More research is
19 needed on how best to deal with composite foods, foods consumed away from home, and extreme
20 values, as well as the best methods for assessing the adequacy of apparent intakes. Ultimately, we
21 recommend sensitivity analyses around key model parameters, and the continual triangulation of HCES-
22 based results with other national and subnational data on food availability, dietary intake, and
23 nutritional status when designing food fortification programs.

24

25 **Keywords**

26 Food fortification; household consumption and expenditure surveys; micronutrients; nutrition; dietary
27 data

28

29 **Statement of significance**

30 In this paper, we synthesized over a decade of research on the use of food consumption data from
31 household consumption and expenditure surveys (HCESs) to inform the design of food fortification
32 programs. From this body of research, we distilled best-practice methods for analyzing HCES data,
33 including the development of a checklist to guide analysts through the process of applying these best
34 practices, and identified research gaps in analytical methods that need to be filled to improve the utility
35 and validity of HCES data for informing the design of fortification programs.

36

37 1. Introduction

38 The successful design and management of food fortification programs bring together a range of
39 information, including characteristics of the local food system, supply chains, consumer behavior,
40 domestic industrial capacity, and costs, among others. Food consumption and nutrient intake data are
41 essential inputs into the design of food fortification programs that effectively increase micronutrient
42 intake and reduce the prevalence of deficiency (1, 2). Ideally, decisions around the relevance and design
43 of fortification programs should be informed by nationally-representative food intake and biochemical
44 data on micronutrient deficiencies (2). However, because of the resource and technical requirements
45 associated with collecting and analyzing individual dietary intake data, they are rarely collected (3-5).
46 Past and ongoing efforts to reduce some of the barriers to conducting large-scale, high-quality dietary
47 intake surveys (e.g., Intake Center for Dietary Assessment and the INDDEx Project, (6)) may increase the
48 availability of these data to inform policy discussions around nutrition intervention programs generally,
49 and food fortification programs in particular. In the meantime, widely-available household consumption
50 and expenditure survey (HCES) data are increasingly being used as a proxy for individual dietary intake
51 data (5). HCES data, which are now collected in more than 100 countries (7), have the benefit of being
52 nationally and, typically, sub-nationally representative, systematically collected every 3-5 years, and are
53 often publicly available online.

54
55 HCESs, also referred to as household income and expenditure surveys, household budget surveys,
56 integrated household surveys, and Living Standards Measurement Study surveys, are designed to collect
57 data on various dimensions of household socioeconomic conditions (2, 5). HCES surveys include modules
58 to collect data on recent household acquisition and/or consumption of food, with significant
59 heterogeneity across countries in the design of food consumption and expenditure modules. The first
60 published use of HCES data to assess fortification programs was in 2007 by Imhoff-Kunsch and

61 colleagues, who used HCES data to assess Guatemala's wheat flour fortification program (8). Then, in
62 2008, Fiedler and colleagues formally advocated for the use of HCES data to inform the development of
63 food fortification programs (9). Over the past decade-plus, HCES data have been used for assessing
64 dietary adequacy and modeling the potential impacts of fortification and other nutrition interventions
65 (5). During this time, limitations and methodological issues associated with the collection and use of
66 HCES data as a source of information on food acquisition and consumption have been identified (10-12),
67 and there have been advancements both in terms of developing recommendations for improved survey
68 design (13, 14) and identifying analytical methods to improve the reliability of estimates based on
69 existing HCES data.

70

71 In this paper, we focus on methods for using existing HCES data to inform the design or redesign of
72 fortification programs, though much of the methodology is applicable to the use of these data for
73 assessing the adequacy of diets more generally or to assess other micronutrient intervention programs
74 (e.g., biofortification). We begin by summarizing the information needed to design effective fortification
75 programs, identifying needs that HCES data might help inform as well as where HCES data are likely to
76 be inadequate and thus alternative data sources are needed. Then, to illustrate specific applications of
77 HCES data, we compile past studies that have used HCES data to answer policy questions about
78 fortification programs. This is followed by a summary of the major limitations inherent in using HCES
79 data for nutrition-related analyses and a review of advances over the past decade in identifying
80 research-based 'best-practice' analytical methods relevant to analyzing existing HCES data for the design
81 of food fortification programs. We also highlight supplementary data that might need to be collected or
82 reviewed alongside HCES data to more fully and accurately provide the information needed to design an
83 effective fortification program. We conclude with an updated list of research gaps in analytical methods

84 that need to be filled to improve the utility and validity of HCES data for informing fortification
85 programs.

86

87 **2. Current status of knowledge**

88

89 2.1 Information needs for fortification program design and the role of HCES data

90

91 The effectiveness of a particular fortification program depends on how well the program is planned,
92 implemented, and monitored to meet its nutrition objectives (15). In practice, fortification programs aim
93 to increase micronutrient supplies to reduce the probability of low intakes in a population without
94 causing risk of excessive intakes (1). Achieving this aim requires data-driven decision making.

95

96 In Table 1, we summarize questions related to identifying nutritional needs and predicting the impacts
97 of fortification that should be addressed during the design (or redesign) phase of a large-scale food
98 fortification program, as well as the information and associated indicators that might be used to answer
99 those questions (1, 2). HCES data can potentially be used to construct some, but not all, of the relevant
100 indicators. In the final column of Table 1, we note some considerations for using HCES data to construct
101 these indicators and circumstances in which HCES data cannot be reliably used and alternative data
102 sources will likely be needed.

103

104 Designing an effective food fortification program begins with confirming that there is a micronutrient
105 deficiency problem of public health significance that merits a large-scale intervention, and that this
106 problem may be effectively addressed by increasing dietary micronutrient intakes (1). Measurement of
107 the prevalence of micronutrient deficiency requires clinical or biochemical data. Supplementing these

108 data with information on which nutrients are insufficient in current diets can be useful to understand
109 the potential causes of deficiency (that is, micronutrient deficiency can be caused by inadequate intake,
110 but health conditions such as infections that alter nutrient metabolism or absorption, or limited
111 bioavailability due to other dietary components, may also contribute). In cases where biochemical data
112 are not available, information on dietary patterns may be used to assess risk of deficiency of specific
113 nutrients. The relevant indicators - mean micronutrient intake and the prevalence of inadequate dietary
114 intake by subgroup - can be estimated using HCES data, but usefulness of these estimates is subject to
115 the limitations inherent in using HCES data, especially for individual-level inferences.

116
117 Identifying appropriate candidate food vehicles - fortifiable foods that are regularly consumed in
118 sufficient quantities by population subgroups at greatest risk of deficiency in a fortifiable (i.e. industrially
119 processed) form - and setting fortification levels require indicators of reach, the “nutrient gap”, effective
120 coverage, and excessive intake that might result from consumption of fortified foods. These indicators,
121 defined in Table 1 (and also in Supplemental Table S1 of terminology used throughout the paper), can all
122 be calculated using HCES data. Potential reach, or the percentage of households or individuals in a
123 target group(s) who consume the fortifiable food(s) in any amount, can be estimated with HCES data as
124 long as the foods under consideration are included in the HCES food list at an adequate level of
125 disaggregation (e.g., oil is listed separately from other fats, and preferably by type of oil), and the list
126 distinguishes between fortifiable (processed) and non-fortifiable (unprocessed) forms of relevant food
127 vehicles and food products made from them (e.g., wheat-flour containing items such as bread and
128 biscuits, in addition to wheat flour). The latter may be determined by information about mode of
129 acquisition (i.e., purchased, produced at home, gifted/shared, etc.). Such indicators can be interpreted
130 qualitatively – that is, they can provide category-based information to inform fortification program
131 design decisions, such as whether or not reach is sufficient to pursue a given food as a fortification

132 vehicle. Indicators that are important for setting fortification levels – e.g., the nutrient gap (defined as
133 the difference between the estimated average requirement and total dietary intake), effective coverage
134 (the change in the prevalence of inadequate intake without and with fortification), and risk of excessive
135 intake - require quantitative interpretations. That is, they help inform the specific concentrations of
136 micronutrients to be added to a food via fortification, which then becomes the basis for establishing
137 fortification standards and for monitoring and regulatory activities. While HCES data can be used to
138 calculate these indicators, in the context of the limitations of HCES data we outline below, using them to
139 help inform decisions surrounding fortification levels requires more caution.

140

141 2.2 Applications of HCES to food fortification

142 Several studies have used HCES data to construct the indicators needed to answer many of the
143 questions identified in Table 1. In Table 2, we summarize a selection of these studies, which, taken
144 together, provide a chronology of examples illustrating how HCES data from a diverse set of LMICs
145 (including countries in Africa, Southeast Asia, Latin America, and the Western Pacific) can answer a
146 range of policy-relevant questions related to fortification program design or redesign. These examples
147 also illustrate the evolution of the use of HCES data, from measuring intake of fortified foods and the
148 amount of nutrients they could deliver (e.g., (8)) to more comprehensive modeling of nutrient content
149 of the rest of the diet and the marginal effects of fortification (e.g., (16, 17)). Parallel efforts examined
150 methodological issues related to HCES analysis, such as comparability of HCES-based results with those
151 based on individual dietary intake data (Supplemental Table S2). Because detailed comparisons of
152 household-level data collection with individual dietary assessment have been conducted in a limited
153 number of contexts, it is difficult to draw broad conclusions about the use of HCES data as a proxy for
154 individual intake. The extent to which individual apparent consumption based on AME estimates will be
155 similar to the results of individual-level data collection will likely depend on the setting, study design-

156 related factors such as the recall period and household survey food list, and the parameters of interest
157 (e.g., proportion consuming a food, amounts consumed, etc.). See Supplemental Materials for additional
158 descriptions of and conclusions based on these comparative studies.

159

160 2.3 Limitations of and “best-practice” methods for use and interpretation of HCES data for nutrition
161 analyses

162 In recent years, there has been a push to improve the reliability and utility of the food
163 acquisition/consumption data collected via HCESs by improving the way the surveys are designed and
164 implemented (5, 10, 13, 18). However, there remains a need to provide guidance on how to analyze and
165 interpret existing HCES data consistently and reliably to inform the design of food fortification programs.
166 This begins with a comprehensive understanding of the limitations and assumptions inherent in the use
167 of HCES data so that methodological choices related to HCES data analysis can be made to understand
168 and reduce the impacts of these limitations, and to help ensure that underlying assumptions and
169 remaining limitations are reflected in the interpretation of results.

170

171 A primary limitation of HCESs is that food consumption or acquisition data are collected at the
172 household-level rather than at the level of individual household members. As a result, indicators based
173 on HCES data are limited to the household level unless additional assumptions about the intrahousehold
174 distribution of food are imposed. Evidence on the validity of these assumptions on intra-household
175 distribution of foods and nutrients is limited (see Supplemental Materials and Supplemental Table S2 for
176 additional information and discussion). Also, HCES data collection instruments typically employ a closed
177 food list to record information about food consumption or acquisition. The specificity of these food lists
178 is, in many cases, another limitation since food lists are oftentimes short, include aggregate foods (e.g.,

179 oils), and/or are missing key foods needed to accurately characterize diets, capture all important sources
180 of nutrients, and assess the potential for fortification of each fortifiable food of interest (10).

181

182 Another limitation of HCESs is that foods consumed away from home (FAFH) are often inadequately
183 captured, if captured at all. Because household consumption is often recalled by one (or several)
184 household members, there is a risk of underreporting of foods consumed by individuals, particularly
185 outside the home. For example, snacks consumed by children at school or foods purchased by a
186 household member while away from home may not be reported. As FAFH become an increasingly
187 important source of nutrients in LMICs, this could lead to an underestimation of total nutrient intake
188 and overestimation of the prevalence of inadequate intake.

189

190 While some HCESs ask directly about household food consumption, others ask only about food
191 acquisition (that is, food acquired via purchase, own production, as gifts, etc. but not necessarily
192 consumed during the recall period) or food expenditures.¹ This may lead to inaccurate estimates of the
193 quantity of food apparently consumed, especially for foods that are acquired relatively infrequently but
194 consumed frequently (e.g., salt), or foods that are acquired in bulk, stored, and consumed over a long
195 period of time (14). A final limitation of HCESs is the lack of survey standardization across countries.
196 HCESs are, justifiably, designed to meet the needs of a specific country and reflect the country-specific
197 context. The resulting cross-country heterogeneity in questionnaires and methods used to collect food
198 data mean that measures derived from them are often not easily comparable and vary widely in quality
199 with respect to nutrition-related measures (10, 13).

¹There is variation across HCESs regarding whether they collect data on household food acquisition (food acquired via purchase, own production, as gifts, etc. but not necessarily consumed during the recall period), and/or food consumption. In an evaluation of food acquisition/consumption data collected via HCESs in 100 LMICs, acquisition data alone were collected 41% of the time, 26% of surveys asked about food consumption, and the remaining 33% asked about both acquisition and consumption (7).

200

201 2.3 Methods for using HCES data for food fortification programs, and “best-practice” analytical methods

202

203 Within the context of these limitation and underlying assumptions and building on the general steps

204 outlined in Imhoff-Kunsch, et al. (19), in Table 3 we provide a checklist for using HCES data. Briefly,

205 before using HCES data, it is important to identify the specific questions of interest with regard to

206 fortification program design or redesign and then thoroughly read the survey documentation and

207 questionnaires to understand the degrees to which HCES data can answer those questions. Then,

208 depending on the nature and intended use of HCES data, there are several steps involved in preparing

209 and analyzing the data, and reviewing and interpreting the results, that require special considerations to

210 identify the most appropriate analytical methods. Given the considerable heterogeneity in the design of

211 food consumption and expenditure modules of HCESs across LMICs (10) and insufficient research

212 comparing analytical methods, it is not possible to identify a set of best-practice analytical methods that

213 apply to *all* existing HCES datasets. However, there are a few common features of existing HCES data

214 that, depending on the analytical methods employed, can influence the reliability of the data for

215 answering some of the key food fortification design questions identified above.

216

217 Presented in Table 4 (in the order in which analysts would generally encounter each issue during data

218 preparation and analysis) are the current research-based recommendations on ‘best-practice’ analytical

219 methods for analyzing existing HCES data to inform the design of food fortification programs. Where

220 research gaps exist such that a best-practice analytical method cannot be identified, we identify

221 ‘common practices’ employed in the literature and, where possible, suggest research activities that

222 could help establish a best practice, highlighting research priorities.

223

224 *Choosing a data collection period in a multi-visit survey*

225

226 The first of these considerations is the data collection period, or the number of times (or frequency) that
227 food data were collected during the survey. This is different from the recall period, which is the number
228 of days over which the respondent is asked to remember and report his/her household's food purchases
229 or consumption. Some HCESs are designed to collect food acquisition and/or consumption data only
230 once with a specific recall period (for example, the enumerator visits the household once and asks,
231 "Over the past seven days, did you or any members of your household consume any rice?"). However,
232 some HCESs ask about food acquisition and/or consumption multiple times during a survey (for
233 example, the enumerator visits a household every two days over a period of 13 days and on each visit
234 asks, "Over the past two days, did you or any members of your household consume any rice?"). In the
235 second example, there would be data on household food consumption over a two-week period,
236 represented as seven data points that each covered two days of recall. Here, the analyst would have a
237 choice between using any one and up to all seven of these data points.

238

239 When using HCES data to inform the design of a food fortification program, it is important for the
240 analyst to be aware of the data collection period and to think strategically about whether to use the full
241 period or a subset of the period since the data collection period may matter in terms of accurately
242 identifying household that consume a particular fortifiable food vehicle and estimating consumption
243 quantities (20). In a recent analysis of HCES data from Bangladesh that allowed for comparison of food
244 data collected from the same households at seven different time periods (at days 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, or 14
245 from the beginning of the survey), the authors found consistency, at both the national- and regional-
246 levels, in the estimates of apparent household consumption of nutrients and the risk of inadequate
247 intake, as well as general dietary patterns, across all data collection periods (20). The conditional (i.e.,

248 among consumers only) and unconditional (i.e., among both consumers and non-consumers) mean
249 quantities of vegetable oil (and other foods that were consumed by almost all households) apparently
250 consumed were likewise consistent across data collection periods. However, for less commonly
251 consumed, non-staple foods, including potentially fortifiable wheat flour, there was significant variation
252 across data collection periods in the percentage of the population apparently consuming these foods.
253 Since there was consistency in the estimates of apparent nutrient intake and risk of inadequate intake
254 across all data collection periods, the recommended best practice (first row, Table 4), then, is to use *all*
255 days of data collection available in the data collection period, which may better reflect usual intake
256 (discussed below). A caveat to this recommendation, however, is that if one of the food vehicles under
257 consideration is not commonly consumed by most of the population, the data collection period should
258 be selected to coincide with the length of time over which consumption of the food vehicle would be
259 nutritionally meaningful (20). For example, consuming fortified flour once every few weeks would be
260 unlikely to increase micronutrient status, so selecting a shorter data collection period might be
261 appropriate for selecting foods to consider fortifying, as this would refine estimates of reach to better
262 capture households that more frequently consumed the fortified food. Because this recommendation is
263 based on only one study analyzing data from one country, further research is needed to establish the
264 external validity of the findings. See the Supplemental Materials for a discussion of the related issue of
265 estimating “usual intake”.

266

267 *Conversion of reported units to standard units*

268

269 Once an analyst has determined the most appropriate period of data collection, one of the next tasks is
270 to calculate the total quantity of each food apparently consumed by converting all quantities to a
271 standard metric unit (typically grams). When recalling the quantity of food acquired or consumed during

272 the recall period, respondents are often encouraged to report the quantity in whatever unit they
273 choose. Allowing respondents flexibility in reporting units rather than constraining them to report
274 quantities in a small set of standard units (e.g., grams, kilograms, liters, etc.) has been found to reduce
275 respondent burden and improve the accuracy of the recalls (13). However, from an analytical
276 perspective, if unit conversion factors are not available for all of the food-and-unit combinations found
277 in the data, the task of converting the non-standard, often locally-specific units (e.g., heap, bowl,
278 bundle, cooking pot) into standard units is non-trivial and involves methodological choices and tradeoffs
279 (e.g., using available data to impute conversion factors, which may be inaccurate, vs taking time and
280 resources to undertake primary data collection to develop conversion factors). In an evaluation of food
281 acquisition/consumption data collected via HCESs in 100 LMICs, conversion to a standard metric unit
282 was not possible in 47% of surveys based on what was available in the data and survey documentation
283 (10). In LMICs generally, and in Africa in particular, reporting in non-standard units is common (21).

284
285 If both quantities of foods consumed and their associated monetary values are reported, and quantities
286 are reported in both standard and non-standard units, one option for converting to standard units is to
287 calculate an average or median price per gram using the quantity and monetary values for all quantities
288 reported in standard units (10). Then, the monetary value of all quantities reported in non-standard
289 units are converted to grams by dividing the reported monetary value by the price per gram. However, a
290 major criticism of this method is that the prices faced by households that tend to choose to report
291 quantities in standard units may be systematically different than prices faced by households that
292 primarily choose non-standard units, resulting in bias in the quantity estimates generated using this
293 method (10). As a result of this potential bias, this method is not recommended.

294

295 The recommended 'best-practice' method, then, is to conduct primary data collection to develop
296 conversion factors for non-standard units reported in the data (see Oseni, et al. (21) for recent Living
297 Standards Measurement Study (LSMS)/World Bank guidelines on conducting market surveys to generate
298 conversion factors). If only the monetary values and not the quantities of the foods acquired or
299 consumed were collected, a market survey can be conducted to generate price per standard unit
300 estimates (i.e., metric prices). While this alternative might be the only option available, metric prices for
301 some foods may change over time independently of inflation, which can introduce error into estimates
302 of quantity based on (inflation-adjusted) metric prices if the market survey is conducted in a different
303 year than the HCES. Further, there may be substantial between-household differences in the prices
304 households face, even households in the same community, depending on quality, bulk purchase
305 discounts, negotiating skills, etc., so this method is likely to produce imprecise household-level
306 estimates (10). Conducting market surveys to generate conversion factors or metric prices will, of
307 course, have time and monetary costs and, as noted above, when conducted after HCES data are
308 collected, may be imprecise. Nevertheless, without conversion factors for non-standard units, the
309 usefulness of HCES data for assessing fortification programs is very limited.

310

311 *Composite foods, foods consumed away from home, and 'other' foods*

312

313 Processing HCES data involves matching each food in the food list to a food composition table (FCT)
314 entry. The accuracy of nutrient intake estimates depends on how well the nutrient contents of the
315 selected FCT entry match the food actually consumed (10), and dealing with issues commonly
316 encountered in food is not always straightforward.

317

318 HCES food lists (and other food lists used to generate indicators of dietary quality) often include
319 composite foods, which are foods that are composed of multiple ingredients that are often consumed in
320 processed form, such as bread, biscuits, or pastries. Composite foods can pose a challenge for analysts
321 when they are included in a food list but do not have accompanying recipe information or cannot be
322 readily matched to a locally-relevant FCT entry. A related challenge is the way FAFH, which includes
323 foods eaten at a restaurant, at a roadside stand, at school, etc., are collected. While most HCESs capture
324 FAFH in some way, there is substantial variation in how this information is collected, ranging from asking
325 a single question about total expenditures on all FAFH consumed during the recall period, to asking
326 about both expenditures and quantities on a short list of, often, very broad categories of FAFH (e.g.,
327 mixed dishes, non-alcoholic beverages) and a very limited number of specific dishes (7). In most cases,
328 data collected on FAFH suffer from significant measurement error (7, 10, 13). Because consuming both
329 composite foods and FAFH is becoming increasingly common in LMICs, and these types of foods
330 therefore represent an increasingly larger share of total nutrients, failing to adequately and accurately
331 account for these foods will lead to an underestimation of food consumption and nutrient intake and an
332 overestimation of the prevalence and severity of inadequate intake (7, 13). Adequately addressing this
333 issue will require improving the way in which the surveys themselves capture composite foods and FAFH
334 (see (13) for specific recommendations), but in the meantime, analysts need to apply analytic
335 techniques to reduce, to the extent possible, underestimation of food consumption and nutrient intake.
336

337 Calorie imputation, a strategy developed by Subramanian and Deaton (22), is commonly used in
338 situations where either only expenditures were collected, where expenditures and quantity were
339 collected for some foods and only expenditures were collected for others, or where both expenditures
340 and quantity were collected but information on nutrient content is not available (7). Calorie imputation,
341 which can also be implemented for other nutrients (e.g., vitamin A imputation), involves first calculating

342 an average price per calorie/nutrient for all foods for which nutrient content data are available. Then,
343 for foods for which that analyst only knows the amount spent, the reciprocal of the average price per
344 calorie/nutrient is multiplied by reported expenditures to estimate the quantity of calories/nutrients in
345 the food (7). However, applying this method to FAFH and composite foods raises concerns related to
346 subnational/geographic variation in prices, quality-related differences in prices, differences in the price
347 per calorie across food groups (i.e., the price per calorie of meat may be much higher than the price per
348 calorie of a staple cereal), and likely differences in the nutrient profile of FAFH compared to foods
349 consumed at home.

350

351 To address these concerns, using data from Bangladesh, Mwangi, et al. (7) explored the effects of
352 varying the methods used to calculate price per calorie/nutrient on apparent caloric/nutrient intake.
353 Data availability limitations and the relatively low nutrient contribution of FAFH and composite foods in
354 Bangladeshi diets precluded the authors from making any definitive statements about both the
355 importance of accounting for FAFH and composite foods for which quantity and/or recipe information
356 are unavailable and also about which of the calorie/nutrient price options described above resulted in
357 the “best” estimates of energy and nutrient intake. The authors concluded that more knowledge about
358 how local contexts (e.g., the degree of heterogeneity in diets) affect food prices and household food
359 demand is needed to identify the most appropriate imputation method, which is likely to be country-
360 and context-specific.

361

362 Another issue that analysts have to contend with is that most food lists include an ‘other’ category for
363 each food group (e.g., other fruits) in which all foods not explicitly listed in that category are captured. In
364 cases where foods included in each of the ‘other’ categories are not specified, one option is to match
365 the ‘other’ category with a single entry from the same good group in an FCT. This might be a reasonable

366 option if it is the most commonly consumed item in that particular category that is not listed explicitly or
367 because all items that would fit into that particular 'other' category are similar in nutrient composition
368 (12). Another option used in the literature has been to take the (weighted) average of the energy and
369 nutrient values for all other foods in that particular category listed in the FCT and assign those averages
370 to consumption captured as 'other' (12, 23). This method may not be particularly useful in
371 circumstances where there is not a relatively local FCT and matches are instead made via several,
372 potentially quite large, FCT databases. If available, the best option might be to use quantitative dietary
373 data from a local dietary study or qualitative data from such a study (i.e., the food list used in the study)
374 to inform the foods included in each 'other' category. If such data are not available, another alternative
375 is to conduct key informant interviews to help identify the most commonly consumed foods that do not
376 appear directly in the food list. Presumably, the calorie/nutrient imputation method described above
377 could also be applied to 'other' foods, though we have not come across this method being used in
378 practice or evaluated for accuracy.

379
380 After food matching has been completed, calculating the main dietary sources of energy and each
381 micronutrient of interest can be a helpful a check to identify and explore unexpected contributors (Table
382 3).

383
384 *Extreme values*

385
386 Although most publicly available HCES datasets are already cleaned to some extent by the implementing
387 organization (24), it is very likely that analysts using the food data from HCESs will encounter extreme
388 values that should be systematically identified and dealt with. Given the nature of HCES food data, it is
389 often difficult to distinguish between extreme values, or outliers, attributable to data errors (stemming

390 from data reporting errors, recording errors, or entry errors) and values that are extreme but potentially
391 legitimate values, such as large bulk purchases (12, 25). Depending on the extent of outliers in the data,
392 the way in which the analyst identifies and addresses extreme values is not likely to have a large impact
393 on population-level prevalence rates and percentages, but indicators based on mean values, such as
394 average apparent consumption and the average nutrient gap, are more likely to be significantly
395 influenced.

396
397 Extreme values for key variables, including apparent energy and micronutrient intake and apparent
398 consumption of fortifiable foods, should be identified and flagged for further scrutiny by visual
399 inspection of histograms or densities and scatterplots. They can also be identified using a general rule of
400 thumb that observations exceeding the 75th percentile by more than three times the interquartile range
401 should be flagged as potential outliers (19). Once flagged, the analyst must decide how to address the
402 extreme values. Deleting extreme values without further inspection is not recommended, since this
403 could compromise the sample weighting scheme and could introduce bias into the sample (25). Rather,
404 as a first step, analysts should try to determine, to the extent possible, whether flagged values are
405 outliers due to data errors or are extreme but plausible values. One way to do this, as recommended by
406 Imhoff-Kunsch, et al. (19), is to cross-check two related variables, such as the reported quantity
407 purchased and the reported amount paid, to determine whether each variable makes sense relative to
408 the other. If not, the extreme value is more likely due to a data error and should be considered for
409 deletion. If related variables agree with one another (e.g., both the quantity purchased and amount paid
410 are high), this is suggestive of legitimately extreme values that might be the result of bulk purchasing or
411 drawing down stocks. Acknowledging that these types of extreme values stem from repurposing food
412 expenditure data as a proxy for food consumption, one strategy employed in the literature is to adjust
413 outliers on the right tail of the distribution by constraining them to be an assumed maximum plausible

414 quantity for daily consumption, while deleting households that reported no food acquisition (12, 26). It
415 should be noted, however, that in the absence of another source of dietary intake data from the same
416 or a very similar population that could be tapped to identify a maximum plausible quantity, setting the
417 constraint values would require either strong assumptions or some primary data collection to inform the
418 values.

419
420 It is difficult to determine a single ‘best-practice’ method for addressing extreme values in HCES food
421 data, since the extent of the problem, and the underlying reasons for the problem, will vary from
422 country to country and survey to survey. Certainly, extreme values should not be ignored, and once
423 identified, they should not be changed or deleted without further inspection. When reporting results,
424 we recommend that a detailed description of how extreme values were detected and addressed,
425 including the number or percentage of observations that were dropped or changed, should be included
426 in the write-up. Also, for indicators that rely on average values, it might be helpful to compare the mean
427 and median values, and if the two values are significantly different, both statistics could be presented.
428 And finally, as noted below, we also suggest running sensitivity analyses comparing all results with and
429 without extreme values that have been deemed to be outliers.

430
431 Since the issue of extreme values will persist even as HCESs are improved, the development of practical,
432 research-based guidelines for identifying and addressing outliers should be prioritized. The guidelines
433 should include guidance on at what stage(s) in the analysis and for what variables extreme values should
434 be identified, rules for how plausible yet extreme values at both ends of the distribution should be
435 treated, and information about which food fortification design indices are most sensitive to extreme
436 values.

437

438 *Assessing adequacy of apparent nutrient intakes with and without fortification*

439

440 Once apparent household food consumption and nutrient intake estimates have been calculated, the
441 analyst needs to decide how to assess dietary adequacy, including whether and how to disaggregate
442 these household measures to the individual level. There are several methods available to disaggregate
443 the data, but since the intrahousehold distribution of food is not observed in the data, each method is
444 accompanied by a set of strong assumptions. One possibility is simply to divide household-level
445 consumption and intake estimates by household size to generate per-capita estimates. This method
446 does not make any adjustments for the demographic composition of a household (e.g., age and sex
447 composition) and is not recommended (27). Alternatively, a commonly employed method that accounts
448 for both household size and variation in household demographic composition is the adult male
449 equivalent (AME) method. The AME method assumes that food is distributed within a household in
450 proportion to each member's age-, sex-, and physical-activity-level-specific caloric needs, and AME
451 weights are derived for each household member that reflect his/her energy requirements relative to the
452 requirements of an adult male (28). Individual-level apparent intake can then be compared to a
453 reference value (e.g., the estimated average requirement (EAR)) to assess adequacy. However, the
454 assumptions underlying the AME method may not be accurate if the intrahousehold distribution of food
455 is not according to members' energy requirements, e.g., if there is gender bias in food distribution
456 within the household. The AME method has been shown to perform poorly for young children in several
457 settings as a result of the difficulty in accurately accounting for energy and nutrient intake from
458 breastmilk and because very young children may not consume the same foods as other household
459 members (29, 30). As such, if fortification design questions are specific to children, collecting individual-
460 level dietary intake data for this group may be necessary. Another potentially important limitation of the
461 AME method is that if household members' physiological state (i.e., whether women are pregnant

462 and/or lactating) is not identified in the HCES data, it is not possible to make appropriate adjustments to
463 energy requirements (and hence AME weights), which may also introduce errors. Given the uncertainty
464 in the distribution of food within households, we recommend analysts perform sensitivity analyses
465 around key assumptions about the intrahousehold distribution of food (e.g., assumed physical activity
466 level of various household members).

467

468 As an alternative to or in addition to a disaggregation method, some analysts have used HCES data to
469 estimate the nutrient density of the household diet (31). Nutrient density is the quantity of a particular
470 nutrient per 1000 kcals of the household diet, which can then be compared to the critical nutrient
471 density² of (a) specific household member(s) (32). If the household nutrient density is above a particular
472 household member's critical nutrient density, the diet is assumed to be of sufficient quality to meet
473 nutrient requirements, assuming the household diet also meets the energy needs of its members. One
474 study compared HCES-based estimates of nutrient density to those based on a 24-hour dietary recall in
475 Uganda and found general agreement between the two data sources for 80% of the nutrients analyzed
476 for WRA and children age 24-59 months (33), suggesting that nutrient density may be an appropriate
477 method for using household-level apparent food consumption data to assess adequacy and may also
478 provide an indicator of the magnitude of nutrient gaps, although similar comparison are needed in other
479 contexts (4).

480

481 Given the current evidence, more research is needed to identify a best-practice for assessing nutrient
482 adequacy with and without fortification. Since this is an issue faced by all analysts using HCES data to
483 assess nutrient adequacy and one that can have a significant impact on findings and how findings are

² Calculated as an individual's nutrient requirement divided his/her energy requirement, multiplied by 1,000.

484 interpreted, research to compare the AME and nutrient density methods and develop best practices for
485 the nutrient density approach should be prioritized.

486

487 **3. Discussion**

488

489 Where individual-level dietary intake data are not available, existing HCES data that are properly
490 analyzed and interpreted, and used in conjunction with other nutrition and health-related data, can
491 provide crucial information for the design of food fortification programs.

492

493 HCES data from high-quality surveys are well-suited to inform fortification program design indicators
494 that can be interpreted qualitatively, such as broad categorizations of population groups by the extent
495 of inadequate dietary micronutrient intake and the reach of food fortification vehicles. However, the
496 evidence on the validity of HCES data for estimating apparent food consumption and nutrient intake,
497 and related prevalence of low or high apparent nutrient intake estimates, at the individual level is mixed
498 and may be particularly unreliable for young children (29, 30, 33-38). As such, there is uncertainty
499 around HCES-based indicators that are important for setting fortification levels, and alternative sources
500 of information may be required to appropriately assess the sizes of the nutrient gaps, effective coverage
501 of food vehicles at varying fortification levels, and risks of excessive intake. Where these estimates are
502 generated, we suggest that the interpretation focus on qualitative assessments of level of risk and on
503 the *relative* predicted impacts of alternative interventions.

504

505 We have highlighted a number of methodological issues that analysts may face when processing and
506 analyzing HCES data to generate indicators for food fortification program design. Following research-
507 based best practices and performing sensitivity analyses around key decisions and parameters will help

508 provide the most reliable estimates possible, given the limitations of the data. For some methodological
509 issues, however, there is insufficient research to support a particular method as being better than other
510 commonly applied methods. These research gaps represent untapped opportunities to provide guidance
511 on the specific methods that will generate the most reliable estimates (typically relative to estimates
512 based on individual dietary intake data such as 24-hour dietary recall data), with implications for the
513 quality of the evidence base from which food fortification design decisions are made.

514

515 There is inadequate research to identify the best methods for assessing the adequacy of apparent
516 nutrient intakes with and without fortification, and given the centrality of this issue in all analyses of
517 HCES data to inform food fortification program decisions, this research should be prioritized. We also
518 suggest prioritizing the development of research-based guidelines for identifying and addressing
519 extreme values in HCES food data as well as how best to account for composite foods, inadequately
520 captured FAFH, and foods categorized as 'other'.

521

522 Another way to improve the quality of HCES-based estimates in specific cases is to collect additional
523 data to supplement the HCES data. We have already noted that where nonstandard unit conversion
524 factors are not available, it is necessary to conduct market surveys to construct these conversion factors.

525 Another example is in cases where shortcomings in HCES food lists preclude consideration of some
526 potential fortification vehicles because they are missing from the list (e.g., condiments being considered
527 for fortification, such as bouillon), the vehicle is combined with other foods within a single food list item,
528 it is not possible to differentiate between fortifiable and non-fortifiable forms of the food based on the
529 listing, or the list is missing composite foods containing the vehicle as an ingredient. These shortcomings
530 could be addressed by conducting Fortification Coverage Assessment Toolkit (FACT) surveys or
531 incorporating indicators derived from the FACT survey method (39, 40). The FACT method, developed by

532 the Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition (GAIN), uses household and market surveys to assess the
533 quality, reach, and consumption of fortified foods using standardized methods and indicators with a
534 particular focus on the collection of information that distinguishes between consumption of the food
535 vehicle in any form, in a fortifiable form, and in a fortified form. To date, FACT surveys have been
536 conducted in more than 16 countries to assess large-scale food fortification programs (40) (see
537 Supplemental Table S3 for a list of countries). The timeframe and costs of conducting a standalone FACT
538 survey are similar to those for conducting any national or sub-national household-level survey (such as
539 HCES); however, if other surveys or surveillance systems are routinely conducted that target the same
540 populations of interest, then FACT modules can easily be added at minimal additional cost to ensure the
541 distinction between the food vehicle in any form vs. a fortifiable form is captured.

542

543 In some instances, the limitations and shortcomings of a specific HCES and/or the questions being asked
544 to design a fortification program mean that the existing HCES food data are simply not an adequate or
545 appropriate proxy for food consumption. Given the heterogeneity in existing HCES data, this is a case-
546 by-case judgement, but one that needs to be carefully considered since relying on inadequate data
547 could result in the implementation of costly, ineffective, and even harmful fortification design decisions.

548

549 Beyond analysis, interpreting the results of HCES data analysis is an important step in using these data to
550 inform the design or redesign of fortification programs. Making the results as useful as possible involves
551 not only relying on the point estimates, but also presenting ranges or confidence intervals based on the
552 standard errors, which account for the survey design and the sampling weights associated with each
553 indicator. Sensitivity analysis should also be conducted around uncertain or particularly influential input
554 variables and methodological choices. Including both ranges and purposeful sets of sensitivity analyses
555 provide means by which the uncertainty inherent in the point estimates, which exists for any dietary

556 intake method but is potentially amplified when using HCES data to proxy for dietary intake, can be
557 communicated to people making decisions about fortification programs. Related, when information
558 generated via HCES data are communicated to decision-makers, the public health problems being
559 addressed should be broadly described using mortality, morbidity, and other data that help set the
560 context for discussion, and the general limitations of using HCES data to proxy for intake as well as any
561 limitations resulting from the specific survey design and implementation should be made clear.

562
563 HCESs, which are widely available at regular time-steps for many LMICs, are a valuable source of
564 nationally-representative information about apparent household food consumption, with the potential
565 to inform the design of food fortification programs as well as other nutrition programs and policies. The
566 utility of HCES data to inform decisions about fortification programs is tempered by a range of
567 limitations that influence the reliability of results for quantitative interpretation, including setting the
568 micronutrient content of selected fortified foods. Some of these limitations can be minimized by
569 following best-practice methods when analyzing the food data collected via HCES. When best practices
570 are followed, HCES data offer numerous advantages over national food supply data, including the
571 opportunity to examine subnational variation in apparent food consumption and nutrient intake.
572 Additional research is needed to fill remaining gaps in our knowledge about best-practice analytical
573 methods.

574

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Table 1. Key questions, information needs, and indicators to inform food fortification program design

Question	Information needs	Indicator(s) relevant to information need	Notes on the use of HCES data to derive indicator
Is a fortification program needed?	What are the micronutrient deficiencies among vulnerable population subgroups (e.g., young children, WRA, rural, poor)?	Prevalence and classification of public health severity of micronutrient deficiencies, by population subgroup, supplemented with data to understand the factors contributing to deficiency (e.g., inadequate intake, infection, bioavailability/absorption, etc.)	Requires biochemical data. HCES data can support understanding of factors contributing to deficiency.
Which micronutrient(s) should a fortification program provide?	What nutrient(s) are lacking in current diets among vulnerable population subgroups?	Mean/median micronutrient intake and prevalence of apparent nutrient intake below the EAR (prevalence of inadequate intake), by population subgroup	Based on apparent food consumption. Individual-level estimates from HCES conditional on assumed intrahousehold food distribution mechanism (e.g., proportional to age- and sex-specific energy requirements). Even if household-level micronutrient availability is adequate, some population subgroups with high needs and/or low priority in terms of intrahousehold food distribution (e.g., young children and women of reproductive age) may not meet their needs. May require individual-level dietary intake data for some subgroups.
Which food(s) should be fortified?	Which foods are regularly consumed in a fortifiable (i.e., industrially processed) form?	Percentage of households that consume the food(s) in a fortifiable form in any amount (reach)	Based on apparent food consumption. Use of HCES data depends on the nature of the food list (e.g., whether fortifiable foods are included in the list at an adequate level of disaggregation and by mode of acquisition).
At what level should micronutrients be added to fortifiable food(s)?	What are the simulated impacts on dietary adequacy at different levels of fortification for selected food(s)?	Average difference between the EAR and total dietary intake in the absence of fortification (nutrient gap)	Same as for reach and prevalence of inadequate intake.
		Percentage of individuals in target group(s) whose nutrient intake status would switch from inadequate to adequate due to the consumption of the fortified food(s) at modeled fortification levels (effective coverage)	Same as for reach and prevalence of inadequate intake.
		Percentage of individuals in target group(s) and other groups whose nutrient intake would exceed the tolerable upper intake	Based on apparent food consumption. If assumptions about the intrahousehold distribution of food are not

		level (UL) due to the consumption of the fortified food(s) at modeled fortification levels (excessive intake)	correct, HCES-based estimates of the risk of excessive intake will be inaccurate in an unknown direction.
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EAR, estimated average requirement; HCES, household consumption and expenditure survey; UL, tolerable upper intake level; WRA, women of reproductive age.

Table 2. Recent studies using HCES data to inform the design and/or management of food fortification programs

Country	Source	Food vehicle(s) and micronutrient(s)	Level of analysis	Study details/questions explored using HCES data	Policy implications
Guatemala	(8) Imhoff-Kunsch et al. (2007)	Wheat flour (iron, folic acid)	National and by SES, rural/urban, and ethnicity	Assessment of existing wheat flour fortification program via: (1) reach, (2) additional micronutrient intake from consumption fortified wheat flour, and (3) percentage of the estimated average requirement met by consumption of the fortified wheat flour.	The likely impacts of wheat flour fortification are modest and have disproportionately low impact among the rural poor. Other fortification vehicles and complementary interventions should be considered.
48 countries	(41) Fiedler and Macdonald (2009)	Vegetable oil and sugar (vitamin A); wheat flour and maize flour (iron, folic acid, b-12, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, b-6, vitamin A, zinc)	National	Evaluation of the feasibility of vegetable oil, sugar, wheat flour, and maize flour fortification in 48 priority countries via: (1) reach, (2) DALYs averted, and (3) cost per DALY averted.	Among feasible fortification vehicles (food apparently consumed by >25% of population, single most cost-effective fortification vehicle was identified for each country.
Uganda	(42) Fiedler and Afidra (2010)	Vegetable oil and sugar (vitamin A)	National	Evaluation of vitamin A fortified vegetable oil program and assessment of additionally fortifying sugar via: (1) reach, (2) additional micronutrient intake from consumption of wheat flour and/or sugar, (3) percentage of the estimated average requirement met by consumption of wheat flour and/or sugar, (4) DALYs averted, and (5) cost per DALY averted.	The reach of the vitamin A fortification program would expand if sugar was also fortified and most benefit those most at risk of vitamin A deficiency.
Guatemala	(43) Fiedler and Helleranta (2010)	Sugar (vitamin A); wheat flour and semolina flour (iron, folic acid, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, b-6, b-12, zinc)	National	Evaluation of existing wheat flour fortification program and assessment of potential modifications (different vehicles and different micronutrients) via: (1) reach, (2) additional micronutrient intake from consumption of the fortified/fortifiable foods, (3) percentage of the estimated average requirement met by consumption of	The impacts of wheat flour fortification are higher than previously estimated. ¹ Additionally fortifying semolina flour could reach households not reached by wheat flour fortification. The potential for excessive intake of vitamin A above the UL should be reviewed.

				the fortified/fortifiable foods, and (4) intake above the UL.	
Zambia	(26) Fiedler et al. (2013)	Sugar and vegetable oil (vitamin A); wheat flour and maize meal (vitamin A, iron, zinc)	National and by income quintile and province	Assessment vitamin A fortified sugar and vegetable oil program and assessment of additionally fortifying wheat flour and/or maize meal with iron and zinc via: (1) apparent nutrient intake and prevalence of inadequate intake, (2) reach, (3) additional nutrient intake via consumption of fortified/fortifiable food(s), (4) reduction in the prevalence of inadequate intake, and (5) intake above the UL.	Additionally fortifying vegetable oil and wheat flour could improve the reach and effectiveness of Zambia's current fortification program. Zambia could consider revising its mandated fortification levels in order to improve effectiveness and/or fine-tune to program to reduce the risk or excessive intake.
Zambia	(16) Fiedler and Lividini (2014)	Sugar, vegetable oil, wheat flour, maize meal, and biofortified maize (vitamin A)	National by rural/urban	Portfolio analysis of existing (sugar fortification and high-dose vitamin A supplementation) and potential (oil, wheat, maize fortification and maize biofortification) vitamin A interventions via: (1) apparent vitamin A intake and prevalence of inadequate intake, and, for each intervention and combinations, (2) reach, (3) additional micronutrient intake, (4) change in vitamin A intake status, (5) DALYs averted, and (6) cost per DALY averted.	Based on cost per DALY averted, introducing vitamin A fortified vegetable oil, wheat flour, and maize meal should be considered. The cost per DALY averted for all six interventions combined over the 30-year period would be "very cost-effective" according to WHO/World Bank classification.
Kenya, Uganda, and Zambia	(44) Fiedler et al. (2014)	Maize meal (iron, folic acid, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, b-6, b-12, vitamin A, zinc)	National	Assessment of the feasibility of maize meal fortification via: (1) reach, (2) cost of national maize meal fortification.	Reach of fortified maize meal is relatively low, though economically feasible (not expected to have a large impact on price or consumer behavior).
Bangladesh	(23) Fiedler, Lividini, and Bermudez (2015)	Vegetable oil (vitamin A)	National by poverty status, rural/urban, and division	Assessment of vitamin A fortified vegetable oil program at the mandated fortification level via: (1) apparent vitamin A nutrient intake and prevalence of inadequate intake, (2) reach (3) additional vitamin A	Validation that oil is an ideal food vehicle for vitamin A fortification in Bangladesh, as effective coverage is consistently high across income levels and geographic subgroups.

				intake by consumption of fortified oil, and (4) reduction in the prevalence of inadequate intake by consumption of fortified oil.	
Bangladesh	(17) Fiedler et al. (2015)	Vegetable oil (vitamin A); wheat flour (iron, folic acid, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, b-6, b-12, vitamin A, zinc)	National by division	Portfolio analysis of existing (vegetable oil) and/or potential (wheat flour) fortification via: (1) apparent nutrient intake and prevalence of inadequate intake, and, for each food vehicle and combined vehicles, (2) reach, (3) additional micronutrient intake, (4) change in nutrient intake status, (5) DALYs averted, and (6) cost per DALY averted.	Based on cost per DALY averted, vitamin A fortified vegetable oil is the most cost-effective. Additionally fortifying wheat flour would also be highly cost-effective and should be considered.
Solomon Islands	(45) Imhoff-Kunsch et al. (2019)	Rice and wheat flour (iron, folic acid, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, zinc)	National and by rural/urban and income quintile	Assessment of fortified wheat flour program and assessment of additionally fortifying rice via: (1) reach, (2) additional micronutrient intake from consumption of the fortified/fortifiable foods, (3) percentage of the estimated average requirement met by consumption of the fortified/fortifiable foods, and (4) intake above the UL.	Apparent consumption of wheat flour is relatively low, particularly among rural households, and impacts of fortification are concentrated among urban households. Apparent consumption of rice is higher so has potential to improve impact of fortification program among all subgroups.
India	(46) Swaminathan et al. (2019)	Salt, wheat flour, and rice (iron)	National and by state	Assessment of fortifying salt, wheat flour, and/or rice with iron, concurrently with iron supplementation, on the prevalence of anemia among women of reproductive age in India and the risk of excessive intake.	Fortification of salt, wheat flour, and/or rice with iron in India may reduce the prevalence of inadequate iron intake among women of reproductive age in some states, but predicted reductions in the prevalence of anemia would be relatively small and variable across states. Intake above UL maybe be a concern in some states, particularly when modeled together with supplementation. The authors

					urge careful consideration of the need for simultaneous iron supplementation and iron fortification of multiple foods.
Nepal	(47) Saville et al. (2020)	Rice (vitamin A, niacin, vitamin B6, vitamin B12, thiamin, folate, iron, zinc, calcium, riboflavin, vitamin C).	National by state, ecological zone, social safety net area, and rural/urban	Assessment of potentially fortifying rice on the prevalence of inadequate intake and risk of intake above the UL.	Modeled impacts of rice fortification at the 2016 WFP recommended levels would help reduce the prevalence of inadequate intake or most nutrients considered, though nutrient gaps would persist for vitamin B12 and iron.
Malawi	(31) Tang et al. (2021)	Vegetable oil (vitamin A) sugar (vitamin A), wheat flour (vitamin A, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, vitamin B6, folate, vitamin B12, iron, and zinc).	National and by administrative region, urban/rural, and socioeconomic position quintile	Assessment of existing vegetable oil, sugar, and wheat flour fortification program based on current and improved fortification compliance on (1) contribution of fortification to nutrient density of the diet and apparent nutrient intake, (2) reductions in inadequacy among WRA.	Fortification of oil and sugar with vitamin A reduced the prevalence of inadequate density and intake except in rural populations of low socioeconomic position. Wheat flour fortification had limited impact on adequacy due to low levels of Additional interventions are likely needed to meet the needs of the most vulnerable.

DALY, disability-adjusted life year; HCES, household consumption and expenditure survey; IFA, iron-folic acid; SES, socioeconomic status; UL, tolerable upper intake level; WRA, women of reproductive age.

¹Note that this is a re-analysis of the work done by Imhoff-Kunsch et al. (8) using more recent HCES data, incorporating additional foods that contain wheat flour, adding an analysis of the predicted impacts of fortifying semolina flour, and, importantly, calculating the impact of fortification based on conditional consumption levels (i.e., amount apparently consumed among those who consumed the product) compared to the unconditional consumption levels used in Imhoff-Kunsch et al. (8).

Table 3. Checklist¹ for using HCES data to inform the design of food fortification programs

Before using HCES data
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify the clear, agreed-upon policy issues to be addressed by HCES data and confirm that HCES data are generally appropriate for informing the agreed-upon policy issues. 2. Read survey documentation to identify and understand: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The survey sampling design and the weighting scheme (including how to use the weights appropriately in the analysis) • The level of representativeness (national, geographic, socioeconomic subgroups, etc.) supported by the sampling design • Survey details/idiosyncrasies that might be important to account for in analyzing the food data or for interpreting the results (seasonality, data collection periods, etc.) 3. Review questionnaires to understand: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The nature and content of the food list (length, aggregate vs disaggregate food items, “other” food items, foods consumed away from home, etc.) • Units of measure for food expenditures/consumption • Length of the food expenditure/consumption recall period • If/how purchased vs home-produced vs gifted/shared foods were captured/differentiated • Extent of overlap between foods in the food list and fortifiable foods of interest • How household demographic information was captured
During data preparation and analyses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify data sources for food composition information and develop an algorithm/hierarchy for selecting a specific food composition source and matching nutrient values to each item in the food list (e.g., match foods to a country-specific food composition table (FCT) first, and if no match is available, match to a regional food composition table, then an international FCT, etc.). 2. Determine methods for estimating nutrient values for “other” foods, aggregate foods, and foods consumed away from home. 3. Select dietary reference values for each micronutrient of interest (estimated average requirements, tolerable upper intake levels, etc.) and energy requirements (for calculation of critical nutrient density). 4. Determine equivalence factors for fortifiable foods of interest contained in processed foods (e.g., proportion of wheat flour in wheat bread). 5. Calculate adult male equivalent (AME) values for each household member and the total number of AMEs per household. 6. Standardize food consumption/expenditures to a common unit of measure (e.g., kgs or grams) and calculate daily apparent household food consumption of each food. 7. Identify extreme values in daily apparent food consumption (see <i>Extreme values</i> subsection below). 8. Estimate total daily household apparent energy and micronutrient intake and/or apparent nutrient density of the household diet and identify extreme values in apparent energy and micronutrient intake/density. 9. If estimating individual intake, use the AME method to estimate apparent individual energy and micronutrient intake. 10. Compare apparent intake and/or apparent nutrient density to reference values (e.g., EAR or critical nutrient density) to determine the prevalence of inadequate or high apparent intake and/or inadequate or high apparent nutrient density of the diet

<p>11. Estimate apparent intake of fortifiable food vehicles of interest.</p> <p>12. Model the impact of food fortification on the prevalence of inadequate or high apparent intake and/or inadequate or high apparent nutrient density of the diet.</p>
<p>During review and interpretation of results</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To identify possible issues with the HCES data, nutrient values, FCT values, or the analysis, consider completing the following analyses at both the national and subnational levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compare average/median apparent energy intake estimates, and their associated ranges and standard deviations, to estimated energy requirements for the population of interest • Calculate the main dietary sources of energy and each micronutrient of interest to identify and further explore unexpected contributors 2. Compare estimates of the prevalence of inadequate intake/nutrient density to estimates of micronutrient deficiency via (e.g.,) national micronutrient survey data². 3. Assess the extent to which the results of this final set of modeling activities addresses the policy issues identified at the outset of this list: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the results consistent with existing information on risk of micronutrient deficiency (based on biomarkers, dietary patterns, anthropometry, etc.)? If not, what might explain areas of inconsistency? • What can we conclude from the analyses based on these data? • What can we <i>not</i> conclude from the analyses based on these data, and what supplemental data collection might be necessary to fill this gap? • How can we interpret and communicate our results to stakeholders, bearing in mind the limitations inherent in using HCES data?

AME, adult male equivalent; EAR, estimated average requirement; FCT, food composition table; HCES, household consumption and expenditure survey.

¹This checklist builds upon the general steps outlined in Imhoff-Kunsch, et al. (19). While the checklist focuses on food fortification, many of the steps are applicable to the use of HCES for other nutrition analyses.

²Inadequate micronutrient intake may not reflect micronutrient deficiency exactly, since other factors such as low nutrient absorption due to infection or disease can also lead to deficiency and the basis for selecting thresholds often differs for low intake vs biomarkers (48).

Table 4. Best- and common-practice analytical methods using HCES data to inform the design of food fortification programs

Methodological issue	HCES characteristic	Best-practice method	Common-practice method	Additional data collection needed	Research gaps
Selecting the data collection period	Food data were collected from households on more than one visit	Use data from all available data collection periods to approximate usual intake unless a food vehicle is not commonly consumed by most of the population, in which case select the data collection period to match the period over which consumption of the food vehicle is nutritionally meaningful.	Not applicable	Not applicable	The best-practice recommendation is based on an analysis from one country, so additional analyses of HCES with data collection periods > 1 are needed to confirm external validity.
Converting reported units to standard units	Some quantities reported in non-standard units (e.g., a bowl heap); monetary values may or may not also be reported	When non-standard unit conversion factors are not available, conduct primary data collection to develop conversion factors for non-standard units reported in the data.	Not applicable	Market surveys to develop non-standard unit conversion factors	None
	Only monetary values reported	Conduct a market survey to generate price per standard unit estimates (i.e., metric prices), then divide the reported monetary value by the price per gram to arrive at quantity in grams.	Not applicable	Market surveys to estimate metric prices	None
Accounting for composite foods and inadequately-captured foods consumed away from home	Not applicable	Not identified	National-level calorie and nutrient imputation	Not applicable	Research how subnational variation in prices, quality-related differences in price, and/or differences in the price per calorie across food groups can be integrated into the price per calorie/nutrient calculations to improve accuracy of imputation.

Accounting for foods categorized as 'other' in each food group	'Other' foods are not specified in the data.	Where available, use quantitative dietary data or qualitative data (i.e., the food list used in a dietary study) to inform the foods included in each "other" category.	Not applicable	Conduct key informant interviews to identify the most commonly consumed foods that do not appear directly in the food list.	For countries where both individual dietary intake data and HCES data have been collected, compare the accuracy of different methods.
Identifying and addressing outliers	Not applicable	Not identified	Flag outliers by visual inspection of histograms, densities, and scatterplots. Observations > 75th percentile by more than three times the interquartile range also used to flag outliers. Cross check flagged values with related variable (e.g., price and quantity) to distinguish data error from plausible extreme values. Drop data errors, and constrain plausible extreme values to maximum plausible quantity for daily consumption.	If information on maximum plausible quantity is not available, primary data collection might be required to establish constraint values.	** ¹ Research-based guidance is needed specifying (1) at what stage(s) in the analysis and for what variables outliers should be identified, (2) rules for how plausible extreme outliers should be treated, (3) and which food fortification design indices are most sensitive to outliers.
Assessing adequacy of nutrient intakes with and without fortification	Not applicable	Not identified	Adult male equivalent (AME) method	To predict the impact of fortification on some target groups for whom the AME, such as young children, method does not perform well, individual-level dietary intake data collection should be collected.	**Research comparing the AME and nutrient density methods and to develop best practices for the nutrient density approach should be conducted. Alternative methods to the AME method, such as statistical disaggregation and predictive modeling,

					should be further explored in terms of their performance in predicting individual-level intake for young children.
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AME, adult male equivalent; FCT, food composition table; HCES, household consumption and expenditure survey.

^{1**}Indicates research priority.

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Supplemental Table S1. Food fortification and household consumption and expenditure survey (HCES) data terminology

Term	Definition used in this paper
Estimated average requirement (EAR)	For a particular age and sex group, the average or median daily nutrient intake level estimated to meet the needs of half the healthy individuals in the group (1).
Usual intake	An individual's long-run average or habitual intake.
Tolerable upper intake level (UL)	For a particular age and sex group, the highest average daily nutrient intake level unlikely to pose risk of adverse health effects to almost all healthy individuals in the group (1).
Apparent food consumption	An estimate of food consumption calculated from household-level reported food acquisition, expenditures, or consumption and assuming no food waste or loss and that all food acquired during the recall period was consumed during the recall period.
Reach	Percentage of households or individuals in a target group(s) who consume the potentially fortifiable food(s) in their fortifiable form in any amount.
Apparent nutrient intake	An estimate of nutrient intake based on apparent food consumption matched with estimates of nutrient content based on (e.g.,) food composition tables.
Nutrient gap	The difference between the estimated average requirement (EAR) and total dietary intake.
Prevalence of inadequate apparent intake	Percentage of individuals in a target group(s) with apparent nutrient intake below the EAR.
Effective coverage	Percentage of individuals in target group(s) whose nutrient intake status would switch from inadequate to adequate due to the consumption of the fortified food(s)
Excessive intake	Percentage of individuals in target group(s) and other groups whose nutrient intake would exceed the UL due to the consumption of the fortified food(s).
Composite foods	Foods that are composed of multiple ingredients that are often consumed in processed forms, such as bread, biscuits, or pastries.
Data collection period	The number of days (or frequency) that food data were collected during a survey.
Recall period	The number of days over which the respondent is asked to remember and report his/her household's food consumption.

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HCES and individual dietary data: Comparability of data sources and analytical methods

Assessments of HCES data as a proxy for individual dietary data

Because HCES data are collected at the household level, estimates of individual apparent food consumption and nutrient intake derived from HCES data necessarily rely on assumptions about the intrahousehold distribution of food (2). A common assumption is that food is allocated relative to each household member's energy requirements. This assumption underlies the "adult male equivalent" (AME) method in which food is divided between individual household members in proportion to each member's age- and sex-specific energy requirements (with assumptions about levels of physical activity and whether women are pregnant or lactating, which are generally not assessed in HCES household rosters) (3). However, these individual level estimates are problematic for assessment of food or nutrient intake if the intrahousehold distribution of food does not follow the assumed pattern. While there is evidence that total energy consumption is likely to align with energy requirements (4), this assumption is less likely to hold for individual foods. For instance, young children are likely to be given different foods compared to older household members, particularly during the complementary feeding period. In addition, breast milk is an important source of nutrition for young children, but HCESs typically do not record information on children's breastfeeding status and, consequently, estimates of apparent intake do not account for nutrients obtained from breast milk (instead, the energy requirements met by breast milk are assumed to come from that child's [energy requirement-based] 'portion' of the household foods). In Cameroon, children had greater reported consumption of wheat flour and sugar relative to their energy requirements compared to women (5). This observation could reflect overreporting of some foods for children (e.g. recall bias) but may also reflect the fact that children consumed foods such as biscuits more often than women (6). Other studies have also found that HCES-based estimates of food consumption among children under five years of age tend to be mis-estimated (7). In contexts where household members eat from a common dish in a specific order, high status members may consume preferred components of the meal (including nutrient-dense meat) while women or children who eat later may consume a greater proportion of broth and staple foods (8, 9). The proportion of snack foods or restaurant meals consumed may also vary depending on whether household members are away from home during the day. While these sources of error are inherent to collection of data at the household level, a key question is whether the estimates generated from HCES data may still be 'close enough' to provide a basis for certain programmatic decisions, particularly when the alternative is to rely on a single national estimate (such as from FAO Food Balance Sheets).

A number of studies have compared estimates of apparent intake from HCES data with the results of individual dietary intake assessments (Supplemental Table S2). These studies examined different dietary components (food groups, specific foods, and/or nutrients) and compared household-level data with varying methods of individual intake assessment (mostly 24-hour dietary recalls (24hr), but also food frequency questionnaires and weighed food records). For some papers (5, 10, 11) interpretation is limited by the fact that the household-level and individual-level data were collected during different surveys. In these cases, the data represent different households selected using different sampling frames and studied at different time points, and thus the results are difficult to interpret because differences cannot be attributed solely to the data collection method.

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We examined six analyses (representing four datasets) in which authors compared food consumption estimates generated by household-level data collection with individual-level dietary assessment within the same households (12-14) whereas other studies reported systematic overestimation (15) or underestimation (16). Among studies that examined age differences, more variation was observed among younger children (<5 years) compared to older household members (7).

In addition, some studies (17, 18) specifically evaluated the AME method by comparing individual 24hr values with an AME-based value estimated by summing the 24hr intakes from all household members and then reallocating consumption based on AME weights. These studies found very good agreement between estimates of food and nutrient intakes, except for younger children (<2-3 years of age), which is likely attributable to breastfeeding and possibly consumption of specific complementary foods.

Overall, it is difficult to draw broad conclusions about the use of HCES data as a proxy for individual intake because detailed comparisons of household-level data collection with individual dietary assessment have been conducted in a limited number of contexts. The extent to which individual apparent consumption based on AME estimates will be similar to the results of individual-level data collection will likely depend on the setting (frequency of eating in the household vs eating outside the home, and how frequently non-household members partake in meals), study design-related factors such as the recall period and household survey food list, and the parameters of interest (proportion consuming a food, amounts consumed, etc.). Given the numerous possible sources of discrepancies between household vs individual-level data sources, household estimates are unlikely to estimate individual intake with high accuracy, particularly for children, who may tend to consume different foods from the rest of the household and for whom breast milk intake is not typically considered in AME-based estimates. Nevertheless, household survey estimates may provide sufficient information for qualitative or semi-quantitative interpretations, for example, to examine relative consumption of different foods or variation in dietary patterns by population subgroup. Estimates can be expected to be more reliable when desired household survey design criteria are met (detailed food list, recording of own production and food consumed away from home, etc.).

Assessments of the adult male equivalent (AME) method

Several studies have assessed the intrahousehold distribution mechanism that underlies the AME method by comparing estimates of food consumption and nutrient intake generated via individual-level to household-level data using data sources that include both household- and individual-level food data. Based on a review of studies from LMICs that included dietary data for adults and for children, Berti (4) compared the amount of energy these different categories of household members actually received to the energy they would have received if calories were distributed according to the AME distribution rules. Of the data from 25 studies across a wide range of LMICs, the author found considerable, nonsystematic variability in the degree to which energy was actually distributed within the household relative to energy requirements across countries and categories of household members, though most were within $\pm 20\%$ of the AME-based distribution. As such, the author concluded that, for the purpose of selecting fortification vehicles and setting fortification levels, it is reasonable to use household-level data and assume that the intrahousehold distribution of food is according to relative energy requirements. To

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evaluate the actual impact of fortification on individual nutrient intake, however, the author suggested that individual-level dietary intake data is needed.

Using datasets from Bangladesh and Ethiopia that each included both household- and individual-level food consumption data, Coates, et al. (17) evaluated the accuracy of the standard AME method as well as several modified versions (nutrient-specific AME weights for iron and protein) in addition to adjusting for meal partakers. The authors found that estimates of nutrient intake based on the standard, energy-based AME method were generally accurate within 10% of the individual-level consumption data with the exception of infants (age 6-24 months) for whom the AME method consistently significantly overestimated intake, which was likely related to the inability to account for breastmilk intake. The construction and use of nutrient-specific AME weights such that intrahousehold distribution was assumed to be according to the relative nutrient (rather than energy) requirements did not improve accuracy, nor did accounting for meal partakers.

Also using data from Bangladesh, Sununtnasuk and Fiedler (18) compared estimates of intake and the prevalence of inadequate intake for energy, iron, vitamin A, zinc, and calcium generated via individual dietary intake data to estimates derived using AME weights. Similar to the findings in Coates, et al. (17), the authors generally found good agreement between the two sets of estimates, with the consistent exception of children age three and under. AME-based estimates for young children were significantly higher than the individual-level estimates for mean intake of energy, iron, vitamin A, and zinc, and the rate of inconsistency prevalence of inadequate intake estimates was higher than other age groups.

Finally, a recent study by Bromage, et al. (15) assessed the performance of several methods to generate individual-level estimates of food and nutrient intake from household-level data – the AME method, statistical disaggregation, and direct predictive modeling - compared to food and nutrient intake from individual-level food consumption data from Mongolia. Statistical disaggregation involves using regression analysis to predict total household food and consumption as a function of household demographic composition variables and other characteristics, and then individual consumption if inferred from the household predictions. This is in contrast to direct predictive modeling, which uses regression to directly predict individual food and nutrient consumption as a function of household and individual characteristics. While the authors found that the statistical disaggregation method generally performed better than the AME method, and that complex direct predictive model estimates provided relatively precise estimates, particularly models that included information on individual-level dietary and eating behavior, ultimately the authors did not recommend one method over the others. Rather, they acknowledged that each method has strengths and weaknesses, and the relative performance of each method depends on survey-specific factors that likely vary between countries. One limitation of this study was that their data did not include individual dietary intake for children, so the authors were not able to assess the relative performance of each method for children, the subgroup for whom the AME method appears to be least well-suited to proxy for individual intake.

Usual intake

Usual intake (i.e., long-run or habitual intake) is commonly applied in the collection and analysis of individual-level dietary intake data. Because nutrient requirements are intended to be met over time, estimation of indicators like dietary micronutrient intake, the gap between intake and the EAR, and the

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prevalence of inadequate intake typically rely on estimates of the distribution of usual nutrient intake in a group or population. In the case of short-term individual-level dietary assessment methods (such as 24-hour dietary recalls), the population distribution of usual intake can be approximated based on more than one non-consecutive day of dietary data for at least some individuals in the sample, which allows for adjustment of the distribution for within-person variation in nutrient intake (19, 20), using, e.g., the National Cancer Institute method (21), to prevent mis-estimation of the prevalence of low or high intakes. Theoretically, household-level data collection would be subject to the same phenomenon: consumption or acquisition measured on a single day may not reflect long-run average consumption. However, there is no guidance available on whether a specific statistical adjustment should be applied to HCES data when analyzed for nutrition outcomes. Since the recall period in HCES is typically longer than a single day (e.g. 7 or 10 days, or even up to one month), the data represent a closer approximation to usual intake compared to short-term dietary assessment tools like 24-hour recalls. In one analysis, including all available days of data did not appreciably change the results, suggesting that adjustment for within-household variation would not have a meaningful impact on fortification program-related conclusions (22).

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Supplemental Table S2. Studies comparing apparent intake estimates from household consumption and expenditure survey data with individual dietary data

Comparison	Source	Geographic region	Assessment methods	Population groups examined	Dietary components compared	Time period(s) compared	Results summary
Different data collection methods in the same households							
	(13) Dary and Jariseta (2012)	Uganda (3 regions: Kampala, Southwestern Region, Northern Region)	(1) 24hr (single recall) conducted in 2008; (2) HCES questionnaire administered to the same households (A2Z-HCES); (3) HCES survey from a different year (2006)	Women 15-49 y; Children 24-59 mo	Fortifiable foods: vegetable oil, sugar, wheat flour, maize flour, rice	Previous day (24hr); previous 7 days (A2Z-HCES and HCES);	Coverage (% consuming over the recall period) was generally higher by HCES compared with 24hr, but similar patterns were observed across population strata. Estimated intakes among “observed consumers” were generally similar, although HCES estimates were lower for wheat flour and rice.
	(14) Jariseta et al. (2012)	Uganda (3 regions: Kampala, Southwestern Region, Northern Region)	(1) 24hr (single recall); (2) HCES questionnaire administered to the same households	Women 15-49 y; Children 24-59 mo	Nutrient density: protein, fat, fiber, calcium, iron, vitamin C, thiamin, riboflavin, niacin, vitamin B6, folate, vitamin B12, vitamin A, zinc, expressed per 2000 kcal	Previous day (24hr); previous 7 days (HCES)	Most (80%) of comparisons of median nutrient density between the 24hr and HCES were not statistically significant. HCES estimates for vitamin B12 were consistently greater in both groups and among strata; for remaining nutrients (including calcium, vitamin C, zinc, and folate), HCES estimates were higher for some comparisons and lower for others.
	(12) Louzada et al. (2017)	Brazil	(1) Household acquisition by 7-day purchase log (Brazil Household Budget Survey); (2) 24hr (2 on nonconsecutive days) among	Individuals 10 y of age and older	Energy, energy from ultra-processed foods & non ultra-processed foods	7-day period; two 24-hour periods	Estimates intakes of total energy, energy from ultra-processed foods, and energy from non-ultra-processed foods by household acquisition were within 10% of individual intakes

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			households in the same survey				inside the home, and within ~20% compared to total intakes.
	(15) Bromage et al. (2018)	Mongolia	(1) Pooled 2012 and 2014 independently-sampled survey waves of the Household Socio-Economic Survey (HSES-HH); (2) 2013 Food Consumption Survey (FCS-HH); (3) 24hr in subset of FCS households (FCS-24)	Individuals that were aged 15 y or older	Food groups; nutrient consumption and consumption-densities (per 100 kcal)	Past week or month (FCS-HH); 10-day period (HSES-HH)	Household-derived mean consumption overestimated dietary-derived mean intake of almost all food groups that were considered. Smaller differences observed for grains groups and milk, and greatest for sugars/sweeteners and non-tuberous vegetables. Generally, the mean of each household-derived per-capita household consumption density (per 100 kcal) of all of the nutrients was within +10% of its corresponding dietary-derived mean
	(7) Karageorgou et al. (2018)	Bangladesh	(1) One 24hr per person in Bangladesh Integrated Household Survey (BIHS); (2) household food consumption over 7 days in the same survey	All household members; stratified results by men/women; 0-5 y, 6-10 y, 11-19 y, 20-44 y, 45+ y	Food groups (9), total energy, macronutrients (8), micronutrients (15)	Previous day (24hr); 7-day period	Estimates from household collection were generally greater than those from 24h recalls for both food groups and nutrients, ranging from 4-8% for seafood and grains to 56% and 242% for non-starchy vegetables and fruits. Total energy was 12% higher and nutrient intakes ranged from 11-55% higher. The degree of difference between the methods varied by individual characteristics (age, sex, etc.). Large discrepancies observed with children 0-5 y (underestimation of milk and overestimation of all other foods).

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	(16) de Oliveira et al. (2019)	Brazil	(1) Household acquisition by 7-day purchase log (Brazil Household Budget Survey); 2) 24hr (2 on nonconsecutive days) among households in the same survey	Individuals 10 y of age and older	Foods and food groups	7-day period; two 24-hour periods	The mean amount of purchased goods was statistically lower than the mean of consumption for most foods, except for rice and sweets. Differences between the methods were smaller when expressed as % of energy contributed. Some differences between methods were smaller when examining only foods consumed at home.
Different data collection methods in different households or surveys							
	(11) Lividini, Fiedler, and Bermudez (2013)	Bangladesh (2 divisions)	(1) OWFR collected from households in 2 subdistricts (2 days in a 7-day period); (2) data for 2 administrative divisions the Bangladesh 2005 National Household Income and Expenditures Survey	Women 15-49 y; Children 24-48 mo	Fortifiable foods (oil, wheat flour, sugar); energy and vitamin A intake pre-fortification and simulated vitamin A intake post-fortification	Previous day (OWFR) vs 14-day diary (HCES)	Energy intake (kcal/d) by OWFR was 73-88% of apparent consumption by HCES. Fortifiable food coverage was similar by method for children but HCES estimates for flour and sugar were higher than OWFR for women. Median consumption (g/d) among consumers varied by food and method, with estimates generally higher by OWFR, but were found to suggest similar fortification levels. Vitamin A simulation results suggested similar rankings of fortification vehicle impact by data source among women but not children.
	(5) Engle-Stone and Brown (2015)	Cameroon	(1) 24hr (repeated in a subset) in 2009 dietary survey; (2) HCES (2007 ECAM3)	Women 15-49 y; Children 12-59 mo	Fortifiable foods: wheat flour, refined cooking oil, sugar, bouillon cube	Separate comparisons between surveys for previous day results and	Previous week coverage (% consuming) in HCES was similar to the FFQ for refined oil and bouillon cube, but lower for wheat flour and sugar.

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						previous 7-day results	Mean frequency of apparent consumption and previous-day coverage were uniformly lower in HCES compared to FFQ. Mean and median amounts (g/d) apparently consumed (among consumers) on the previous day were generally within 50% of the 24hr value, with some exceptions. Similar patterns of consumption observed by geographic region and socioeconomic status.
	(10) Aleksandrowicz et al. (2017)	India	(1) 24hr (two national surveys); (2) FFQ (2 regional surveys); (3) HCES (6 national surveys)	Adults 16-59 y (men and women)	Total food intake and food groups (g/person/d): cereals, pulses, dairy products (including butter), vegetable oils, meat (including fish), eggs, fruits and nuts and vegetables (including root vegetables)	Previous 30 days (HCES), previous year (FFQ), previous day (24hr)	Variation between FFQ vs HCES ranged from -24% for vegetables and sugar to 212% for eggs. Variation for 24hr vs HCES ranged from -55% for sugar to 25% for pulses.
Assessment of AME approach with summed 24-hour recall data							
	(18) Sununtnasuk and Fiedler (2017)	Bangladesh	(1) one 24hr per person in Bangladesh Integrated Household Survey (BIHS); 2) AME-based intakes calculated by	All household members	Nutrients: energy, iron, vitamin A, zinc, calcium	Previous day (24hr)	Prevalence of inadequate energy and nutrient intakes were generally within 10% for children 4 years and older, but AME-based estimates over-estimated intake for younger children, particularly children <1 year of age (likely due to contribution of breastfeeding)

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			summing 24hr data from all household members				
	(17) Coates et al. (2017b)	Bangladesh (2 divisions); Ethiopia (3 regions)	(1) 24hr (two in Bangladesh; one in Ethiopia); (2) AME-based intakes calculated by summing 24hr from all household members	All household members	Nutrients: energy, protein, and iron	Previous day (24hr)	For energy and iron intake, the % difference between individual intake and AME-based estimates was generally <10% for all age groups in Ethiopia and for groups of age 2 years and older in Bangladesh. Protein intake was generally within 15%, even among young children.

24hr, 24-hour dietary recall; AME, adult male equivalent; FFQ, food frequency questionnaire; g/d, grams per day; HCES, household consumption and expenditure survey, mo, months; OWFR, observed weighed food record; y, years.

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Fortification Assessment Coverage Toolkit (FACT) surveys

Supplemental Table S3. Fortification Assessment Coverage Toolkit (FACT) surveys assessing large-scale food fortification programs conducted between 2013-2017

Country	Scope
Afghanistan	National
Bangladesh	National
Cote d'Ivoire	Abidjan
Ethiopia ¹	National
Ghana ¹	National
India ¹	National
India, Rajasthan	Rajasthan
Indonesia ¹	National
Kazakhstan	National
Niger ¹	National
Nigeria	Kano and Lagos states
Nigeria	Sokoto and Ebonyi states
Pakistan	Balochistan, Punjab, and Sindh provinces
Philippines ¹	National
Senegal	National
South Africa	Eastern Cape and Gauteng provinces
Tanzania	National
Uganda	National

¹FACT modules included in Universal Salt Iodization (USI) Partnership Project surveys to assess salt iodization programs

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